

Experimental

Standard solutions of Ru and Pt were prepared by dissolving the corresponding chlorides (A.R.) in HCl and standardised by the usual method^{9,10}. BDTC was synthesised¹¹ and purified by crystallisation from benzene. Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer with optically matched quartz cells (1 cm). A Elico LI-10 pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Procedure: To a sample solution containing 50 µg of Ru^{III} or 97.55 µg of Pt^{IV} was added of 1.0×10^{-2} M BDTC solution (4 ml) in acetone. For Ru, the pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.0. For Pt^{IV}, 0.1 M stannous chloride solution (2 ml) was added and pH adjusted to 0.3. The solution was heated to 100° for 1 h on a water-bath and then allowed to cool and equilibrated by shaking for 15 min with chloroform (10 ml). The absorbance of the dry extracts were measured at 425 nm for Ru^{III} and 352 nm for Pt^{IV} using the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

It was found that 80-fold and 30-fold molar excess of BDTC were necessary for complete extraction of Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV}, respectively. Same concentration of the reagent was maintained in the subsequent studies. The Ru^{III} and the Pt^{IV} complexes with BDTC gave same λ_{\max} in solvent, like benzene, toluene, *p*-xylene, cyclohexane, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and carbon disulphide, but the absorbance values were different. Chloroform was found to be the best solvent as the complexes showed highest distribution ratio in it.

A minimum of 70 min heating time was required to develop the maximum colour intensity and the extracts were stable for at least 5 h at $27 \pm 2^\circ$. The period of equilibration was varied from 0.5 to 20 min and the extraction was found to be quantitative after 10 min. The complexes obey Beer's law upto 8.4 and 11.1 ppm of Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV}, respectively. The molar absorptivities of the Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV} complexes were found to be 4.2×10^3 and 9.3×10^3 dm² mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, respectively. Sensitivities in term of Sandell's definition¹², were 0.023 8 µg cm⁻² Ru^{III} and 0.020 96 µg cm⁻² Pt^{IV}. Relative errors were $\pm 2.1\%$ for Ru^{III} and $\pm 1.1\%$ for Pt^{IV}.

Effect of foreign ions: Among the cations (added as chloride, nitrate or sulphate), 100-fold of Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Cu^{II}, Rh^{III}, U^{VI}, Th^{IV} and alkali metal ions do not interfere. Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} interfere seriously in Ru^{III}; and Pd^{II}, Cd^{II}, Fe^{III} and Hg^{II} interfere seriously in Pt^{IV}. Among anions, 300-fold excess of acetate, tartarate, borate, molybdate, bromide, iodide, triocyanate (added as alkali metal salts) do not interfere. Tolerance limit of nitrite and fluoride ions are quite low in case of Pt^{IV}.

Stoichiometry and stability of complexes: The molar composition of Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV} chelates of BDTC was determined by mole ratio method¹³ and Job's method¹⁴ of continuous variation. The two methods indicated the formation of 1:1 complex in either of the case. The log K values (K=stability constant) for Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV} complexes were found to be 4.8 ± 0.05 and 5.5 ± 0.05 , respectively.

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Cation Exchange Chromatographic Separation of Nickel in Mixed Solvents

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THE cation exchange chromatographic studies of nickel were attempted in mixed solvents¹⁻³ with hydrochloric acid. Nitric acid⁴ and hydrobromic acid⁵ were also used with methanol and acetone. Such methods were not selective as ions forming anionic complexes showed strong interferences. Thus work on the separation of less common elements from nickel was lacking. Such studies are reported in this paper.

TABLE 1—CATION-EXCHANGE STUDIES OF NICKEL IN MIXED SOLVENTS

Organic solvent with 2 M HCl	%	Peak elution volume V_{max} ml	Total elution volume V_t ml	Ni recovery %	Elution constant (E)	Volume distribution coefficient D_v	Weight distribution coefficient D_w
HCl 2 M		75	250	98.9	0.58	1.74	1.21
Methanol	20	75	250	100.9	0.58	1.74	1.21
	40	75	250	99.9	0.58	1.74	1.21
	60	100	250	87.7	0.89	2.55	1.77
	80	100	250	81.8	0.89	2.55	1.77
Ethanol	20	75	250	100.0	0.58	1.74	1.21
	40	100	250	84.5	0.89	2.55	1.77
	60	125	250	54.8	0.80	3.86	2.88
	80	150	250	27.4	—	—	—
2-Propanol	20	75	250	100.1	0.58	1.74	1.21
	40	75	250	99.9	0.58	1.74	1.21
	60	150	250	72.8	0.24	4.17	2.90
Acetone	20	75	250	97.6	0.58	1.74	1.21
	40	100	250	95.5	0.89	2.55	1.77
	60	125	250	84.0	0.80	3.86	2.88
	80	100	250	68.8	0.89	2.55	1.77

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF NICKEL FROM MULTICOMPONENT MIXTURES IN MIXED SOLVENT SYSTEMS

Sl. no.	Element	Amount added mg	Amount found mg	Recovery %	Eluant
1.	Zn	10.0	10.0	100.0	0.1 M HCl in 80% THF
	Pb	9.40	9.40	100.0	0.25 M HCl in 80% acetone
	Cu	8.80	8.70	98.8	1 M HCl in 80% ethanol
	Ni	10.0	9.90	99.0	2 M HCl
2.	Fe	9.20	9.20	100.0	0.25 M HCl in 80% acetone
	Cu	8.80	8.70	98.8	0.5 M HCl in 80% THF
	Mn	10.20	10.10	99.0	0.75 M HCl in 90% acetone
	Ni	10.0	10.0	100.0	2 M HCl
3.	Bi	10.0	10.0	100.0	0.25 M HCl in 20% THF
	Ca	7.50	7.45	99.3	0.5 M HCl in 40% 2-propanol
	U	10.0	9.98	99.8	1 M HCl in 80% acetone
	Ni	10.0	9.85	98.5	2 M HCl in 80% THF
	Th	12.50	12.50	100.0	1 M H ₂ SO ₄

Experimental

The apparatus, reagents and column used were similar to one described earlier⁶. A stock solution of nickel was prepared by dissolving nickel sulphate (AnalaR) (5.65 g) in distilled water (250 ml) containing 1% sulphuric acid, and was standardised as usual. It contained 5.1 mg ml⁻¹ of nickel.

General procedure: An aliquot containing 10 mg of nickel was passed through the column. After washing the column, nickel was eluted with mineral acids, salts and the mixtures of 2 M HCl with methanol, ethanol, 2-propanol, acetone, 1,4-dioxane or tetrahydrofuran (Table 1). The effluent lot was collected in twelve fractions (25 ml), and nickel from each fraction was determined complexometrically.

Results and Discussion

The selectivity scale for eluant was HCl > H₂SO₄ > HNO₃ > HClO₄, while in the presence of 2 M HCl

the selectivity scale for mixed solvents was methanol > THF > acetone > dioxane > propanol > ethanol. Hydrochloric acid was used with advantage with methanol, ethanol, 2-propanol and 1,4-dioxane (20-40%). However, acetone and tetrahydrofuran were poor eluants in high concentrations (Table 1).

Separation of Ni from binary mixtures: It was noted that 2 M HCl in 80% methanol was efficient eluant for Ni, but not for Sc, Y, Th, La and Ce. Similarly, 2 M HCl and 80% acetone was best eluant for Ni but not for Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba and Al. Hence, in such mixtures, Ni was first eluted by these eluants and other ions were eluted in binary mixtures with 4-8 M HCl. Further more it was observed that 1 M HCl in 90% THF was efficient eluant for Fe^{III}, Mn, Co, Cu^{II}, U^{VI} and Ga^{III} but not for Ni^{II}, so also 0.25 M HCl in 80% 1,4-dioxane was efficient eluant for In^{III}, Bi^{III}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} but not for Ni^{II}, hence these ions were eluted first with these eluants followed by the elution of Ni with 2 M HCl.

Separation of Ni from multicomponent mixtures : Ni was separated from multicomponent mixtures by exploiting the difference in elution with HCl in the presence of different concentration of different kinds of non-aqueous solvents. It was possible to separate Ni from complex mixtures containing Zn, Pb, Cu, Fe, Mn, Bi, Cd, U and Th. The details of such separation are shown in Table 2.

The separation of Ni from Cu, Fe, Mn, Cd and Al is important as they are generally associated with one another in alloys. The isolation of Ni from Zr, Th, Ce, U and Ba has practical application. The overall operation for the separation and determination does not exceed 3 h. The results are reproducible.

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Aas Determination of Tin in various Samples after Extraction with Liquid Anion-exchanger

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VARIOUS carboxylates of tin(II) compounds have been reported¹. The present communication reports the extraction behaviour of tin as $\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})_2^{2-}$ with liquid anion-exchanger, Aliquat 336, in benzene. The determination of tin have been carried out by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (aas).

Experimental

Aliquat 336 (Fluka, A.G.) liquid anion-exchanger was used without further purification. A stock solution of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR) was prepared and the solution was standardised² before use. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade. A Shimadzu 646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer with a tin hollow cathode lamp was used, and the conditions were optimised according to its manual. The pH values were measured with a Systronics 331 expanded pH meter.

The general procedure was based upon solvent extraction technique. The aqueous phase was made up from a 5.0 ml of the solution containing 237.38

μg of tin ; 0.05 M oxalic acid solution (2.0 ml) was added, pH of the resulting solution adjusted to 2.3 and finally phthalate-buffer (1.5 ml) added. Then the aqueous phase was made up to 10 ml and was equilibrated in a separatory funnel with 5% (v/v) Aliquat 336 in benzene (10 ml) for 5 min. The two layers were allowed to settle for 10 min. The organic phase was then separated carefully to another separatory funnel. In order to remove the organic solvent entrained in the separated aqueous phase, the latter was washed with benzene (5 ml). The resulting extract was mixed with the earlier separated organic phase. Then 2 M HNO_3 (10 ml) was added to the organic phase and the mixture was shaken for 5 min. The two phases were allowed to settle. The aqueous phase was carefully separated and again washed with benzene (5 ml) to remove any entrained solvent present in the separated aqueous phase. The amount of tin extracted was estimated by aas in presence of 1000-fold excess NaNO_3 , which enhanced the tin absorption by about 20%³.

Results and Discussion

Extraction of tin complex became quantitative in the pH range 2.0-2.6. Quantitative extraction of tin occurs with benzene (97.3%), and extractions with other solvents show 94.6% in carbon disulphide, 91.9% in toluene, 83.8% in nitrobenzene, 75.7% in 1,2-dichloroethane, 70.3% in isobutyl methyl ketone, 59.5% in amyl alcohol and 35.1% in chloroform. It was found that the extraction increased with increasing extractant concentration and was complete at 5% Aliquat 336. The extraction time was quantitative within 2 min and stripping complete within 3 min, and it was maintained 5 min in both the cases. For the determination of tin, tolerance limits (within an error of $\pm 2\%$) for various ions are as follows : Al^{III} , Cr^{III} , Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Pb^{II} (all 40-fold) ; Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , sulphate (all 80-fold) ; Fe^{III} , phosphate (all 12-fold).

The extraction of $\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})_2^{2-}$ is quantitative provided the Aliquat 336-tin mole ratio is ≥ 2 . Plot of log D against log [Aliquat 336] provides a straight line with slope around 2. Thus the simple extraction mechanism of Sn^{II} may be represented as

where, o = organic phase and a = aqueous phase.

Analyses of tin in different samples : Several samples were analysed for tin contents after decomposition by the standard methods (Table 1). Solder, a certified sample (59.9% Sn), was decomposed⁴ and

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF TIN IN VARIOUS SAMPLES

Sample	Amount taken g	Sn found* mg g ⁻¹	Standard deviation
Solder	0.101 00	594.658	± 0.043
Toothpaste	3.344 08	0.161	± 0.011
Vegetable oil	9.558 20	0.016	± 0.002

* Average of 4 determinations